

THE INFLUENCE OF EULER CRITICAL LOAD ON THE METHOD OF INITIAL PARAMETERS FOR THE DYNAMIC ANALYSIS OF A MULTI-STOREY BUILDING SUBJECTED TO AERODYNAMIC FORCES

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ABSTRACT

This research work used a combination of the method of virtual works and Euler's critical load to determine modified stiffness, angular frequency and later the generalised flexural rigidity EI_{on} by taking into consideration the influence of axial load and consequently the total modal mass (m) on the model (multi-storey building). The study used these modified and assessed quantities, on the original equations governing the method of initial parameters to transform them from one hitherto recognised as suitable for the design of a beam on elastic foundation; to another one now proposed to be suitable for the analysis of tall structures such as the model (Multi-storey building). The information gained was used to determine the fundamental natural and characteristic mode of vibration through which the dynamic wind loadings for the 72m, 20 storey building were assessed. The study revealed that the use of Total Modal Mass (TMM) instead of Linear Modal Mass (LMM) will lead to a better assessment of the dynamic loading and consequently occupancy perception level or motion of the building when subjected to the dynamic wind pulsation. It is however rather interesting or disturbing to observe that, while all the Kirlov influence functions tend to converge at the top of the model (at 72m); which is clearly an indication of instability; since the influence parameters are narrowly distributed with increase in height. Therefore, stress concentration may occur in such structures and may be classified to be unsafe. This may well be pulsing indications that render these influence functions unsuitable for use on structures taller than 72m or less. In contrast; the proposed influence functions are sparsely distributed starting from the base of the model and remain highly sensitive with increase in height. In fact, the point of convergence has been remarkably or reasonably increased. Therefore, from the authors' point of view, this development shows the study has successfully increased or expanded the height of applicability of the method of initial parameters well beyond what can be seen as its former upper limit caused mainly by the influence of the modifications and transformations of the governing equations and the influence functions.

KEYWORDS: Euler critical load, method of initial parameters; elastic line; fundamental characteristic mode of vibration; generalised stiffness; influence functions.

INTRODUCTION

Relatively few data exist for the assessment of direct wind force. The complete description of wind speeds as acting on a structure to generate wind forces will require consideration of the variation of wind speeds from point to point on the structure, and the response of the structure itself.

Sudden variation in wind speed is called gustiness or turbulence and very important in determining building oscillation. Wind loads associated with gustiness or turbulence change rapidly and even abruptly, creating effects much larger than if the same load were applied statically or gradually and therefore, need to be studied as if they were dynamic in nature. The intensity of wind depends on how fast it varies and also on the response of the structure (Mendis *et al*, 2007).

Taranath (2005), there has been persistent destruction of lives and property caused by direct or indirect effects of wind storms. Windstorms pose variety of problems to buildings (in particular for tall buildings) and constitute the largest cause of economic and insured losses in many countries and Nigeria is not an exception.

Windstorms that are of interest for the design of buildings are classified into three major types; Prevailing winds, Seasonal winds and Local winds. The action of wind gust depends on the generalized fundamental natural period of the building. The wind gust is dynamic, if it reaches its maximum value and vanishes in a time much shorter than the generalized fundamental natural period of the building or structure and static, if the wind load increases and vanishes in a time much longer than the generalized fundamental natural period for the building.

When multi-storey steel framed building or other forms of deformable tall structures are subjected to dynamic loadings such as harmonic excitation, it is forced to vibrate at the some frequency of excitation. These excitations may be undesirable or harmful to the structural integrity of such tall structure, human perception or the safety of equipment or structure when large vibration amplitudes develop. To prevent large amplitudes from developing, dampers and absorbers are often used (Kareem *et al.*, 1999).

Mario (1991), when a dynamic system is excited by a suddenly applied non-periodic excitation $F(t)$, the response to such excitation is called transient since steady-state oscillations are generally not produced and poses no problem to the structure; if however, the suddenly applied load is periodic excitation $F(t)$, the response to such excitation produces a steady-state oscillations which may be harmful to the structural system. Therefore, the objective of this work is to study the influence of steady state oscillations caused by the effects of dynamic wind pulsation on a multi-storey braced steel framed shear wall or other forms of tall structures.

According to Mario (1991) and Nakashima *et al.*,(1992) in designing a high - rise building which satisfies the serviceability requirements such as perception and comfort of occupants, the fundamental natural period is a very important design variable. This is very crucial since the design dynamic loading that causes the vibration of the building under the influence of wind induced vibration or wind pulsation is usually influenced by the fundamental natural period and characteristic fundamental natural mode of vibration.

Therefore, to effectively and efficiently design tall buildings against the dynamic effect of wind, considerations such as the site basic wind speed, building dimensions, shape, and stiffness, damping ratios, site topography, climatology, foundation type, boundary layer meteorology, bluff body aerodynamic and probability theory are important.

The oscillator of the structural system is naturally wind forces or its gustiness; method of computation for the minimum natural frequency of the system was developed for beam on elastic foundation by Kirlov as reported by Christev *et al.*, (1974) without considering the influence of Euler’s critical load. This method was subsequently used by Onundi and Adeniji (1996) for the dynamic analysis of multi-storey building, the method of linear modal mass was adopted. This approach does not reflect the actual practical situation for a multi-storey building because the axial load will always act along with the moment in the stanchions and will usually affect the final result for a correct assessment of tall structures such as telecommunication masts or high rise buildings for dynamic analysis. Therefore, this paper attempts to highlight the vital effects the Euler critical load is expected to have on the influence functions of the method of initial parameters which is popular for the dynamic analysis of beam on elastic foundation or multi-storey building.

The Method of Initial Parameters

This method considers the dynamic theory of beams for which governing equations of motion are partial differential equation given as:

$$\frac{d^2y(x, t)}{dt^2} + \frac{EI d^4y(x, t)}{m_i dx^4} = 0 \quad \dots\dots 1$$

Equation 1 can be written as

$$y(x, t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} A_n X_n(x) \sin(\omega_n t + \phi_n) \quad \dots\dots\dots 2$$

if $T(t) = A_n \sin(\omega_n t + \phi_n) \quad \dots\dots\dots 3$

then equation 2 becomes

$$y(x, t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} X_n T(t) \quad \dots\dots\dots 4$$

$y(x,t)$ is the deflection of the bar axis , which is dependent upon time and the bar length.
 For flexural members (beams on elastic foundation) of uniform section and uniform distributed mass, subjected to long term natural harmonic vibrations, the use of the above differential equation results in the four relationships for the amplitudes of deflections, rotations, moments and shear forces at any section (the initial parameters method in structural dynamics).

$$\begin{aligned} y(x) &= y_0 A_{kx} + \frac{\alpha_0}{k} B_{kx} + \frac{M_0 C_{kx}}{EI k^2} + \frac{Q_0 D_{kx}}{EI k^3} \\ \alpha(x) &= k y_0 D_{kx} + \alpha_0 B_{kx} + \frac{M_0 B_{kx}}{EI k} + \frac{Q_0 C_{kx}}{EI k^2} \quad \dots\dots\dots 5 \\ M(x) &= EI k^2 y_0 C_{kx} + EI k \alpha_0 D_{kx} + M_0 A_{kx} + \frac{Q_0 B_{kx}}{k} \\ Q(x) &= EI k^3 y_0 B_{kx} + EI k^2 \alpha_0 C_{kx} + k M_0 D_{kx} + Q_0 A_{kx} \end{aligned}$$

Where y_0 , α_0 , M_0 and Q_0 are respectively the amplitudes of deflections, rotations, moments and shear forces at the initial section ($x=0$); y_i and α_i are respectively the deflections and rotations at the section where the lumped mass are located.

$$k = 4 \sqrt{\frac{q \omega^2}{gEI}} \quad \dots\dots\dots 6a$$

k . is the stiffness of the bar (beam)
 ω is the frequency of the natural frequency of the system.
 g . the acceleration due to gravity, 9.81 m/sec²
 q . the weight per unit length of the beam, including the distributed load (if any) but

$$m_i = \frac{q}{g} \quad \text{where } m_i \text{ is the linear modal mass of the beam}$$

Therefore,

$$k = 4 \sqrt{\frac{m_i \omega^2}{EI}} \quad \dots\dots\dots 6b$$

A_x , B_x , C_x and D_x are the influence function given by

$$\begin{aligned} A_{kx} &= 0.5 (\cosh kx + \cos kx) \\ B_{kx} &= 0.5 (\sinh kx + \sin kx) \\ C_{kx} &= 0.5 (\cosh kx - \cos kx) \quad \text{and} \\ D_{kx} &= 0.5 (\sinh kx - \sin kx) \quad \dots\dots\dots 7 \end{aligned}$$

These results were derived by Kirlov and reported in Christev *et al* (1974). The formulae of the method of initial parameter given above can also be employed to determine the natural frequency spectrum of the system.

Equations (5) can also be used to solve framed system. This method was applied to dynamic behaviour of flexural members (beams on elastic foundation) and not for multi-storey buildings until recently when it was used as method of linear modal mass (Onundi and Adeniji 1996). The results obtained using equation (5) produced the fundamental characteristic mode of vibration for beam. In order for this method to be applied to the dynamic analysis of multi-storey buildings, the stiffness value (k) and moment of inertia (I) in equation (5) were modified.

Description of the Model for the Multi-Storey Building

The building under investigation is a 20-storey steel framed structure measuring 12 m by 24 m in plan and 72 m in height. It is enclosed at all sides to its full height, with steel-framed glass curtain walls. The partition walls are effectively constructed with light weight stud walls. The proposed building is assumed to be situated on a slightly gentle hilly terrain in an open area after the School of Environment Design, Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi in Nigeria where it is exposed to winds blowing from all directions. Figure 1 shows the structural model used for the investigation of the building is a substitute cantilever with finite lumped masses subjected to Euler critical load.

Figure 1: Substitute Cantilever of the Multi-Storey Building

This enables us to reduce the design of a deformable structure to that of an elastic column in with several lumped masses are concentrated on it, with the aerodynamic loadings creating a time dependent displacement $\Delta(t)$ of the upper end of the structural system.

A typical model of one degree of freedom cantilevered system with applied loads as shown on the model (Figure 1) is given as:

$$EI\delta_{ik} = \sum \int (M_i M_k) ds' \dots\dots\dots 8$$

$$EI\delta_{11} = \sum \int (M_1^2) ds' = \frac{L^3}{3} \dots\dots\dots 9$$

$$\therefore \delta_{11} = \frac{L^3}{3EI} \quad \dots\dots\dots 10$$

However,

$$k(\text{spring constant}) = \frac{1}{\delta_{11}} \quad \dots\dots\dots 11$$

and

$$\omega_{\min} = \sqrt{\frac{k}{m_i}} \quad \dots\dots\dots 12$$

i.e. $\omega_{\min}^2 = \frac{k}{m_i}$

$$\therefore k = \omega_{\min}^2 m_i \quad \dots\dots\dots 13$$

Equation (13) is the stiffness without Euler's critical load
Substituting equation 13 into 11 and 10,

$$\omega_{\min}^2 = \frac{3EI}{m_i L^3} \quad \dots\dots\dots 14$$

ω_{\min} is the minimum natural frequency of the system without Euler's critical load. This does not reflect the practical situation for a multi-storey building because the axial load will always act along with the moment in the stanchions. Therefore, when Euler's critical load is considered, according to (Fenner, 1989 and Kratav *et al.* 1974), we have the modified stiffness as:

$$k = \frac{3EI \left(1 - \frac{P}{P_{cr}}\right)}{L^3} \quad \dots\dots\dots 15$$

Since Euler critical load is now called into play, the initial stiffness value k in equation (13) is replaced by the modified value of stiffness k_m

Substituting into equation (15), the values of:

- P = m g;
- P = Euler critical load
- Where $m = \sum m_i = \sum m_1 + m_2 + m_3 \dots\dots\dots m_n = n_s m_i$
- $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots\dots\dots n$
- $g = 9.81 \text{ m/sec}^2$
- $P = \pi^2 EI / 4 L^2$

$$k_m = \frac{3EI \left(1 - \frac{4mgL^2}{\pi^2 EI}\right)}{L^3} \quad \dots\dots\dots 16$$

But $k \propto I$, therefore the modified moment of inertia is taken as I_{on} as shown in equation (17) to give the modified natural frequency for a multi-storey building.

$$\omega_{min} = \sqrt{\frac{3EI_{on} \left(1 - \frac{4mgL^2}{\pi^2 EI_{on}} \right)}{mL^3}} \dots\dots\dots 17$$

Nakashima *et al.*, (1992) as reported by Dowling *et al.*, (1992); in their work, “*simple expression for predicting fundamental natural periods for high rise building*”; surveyed the fundamental natural periods of a total of 239 high – rise steel buildings designed and built in Japan between 1968 and 1988. They confirmed that all the periods were obtained by eigenvalue analysis, in which the building was modelled as a discrete spring – mass system with the weight of storey lumped as one discrete mass and the storey stiffness representing one elastic spring. They compared these results with measured values and in particular with the relationship between the fundamental natural period, T and base shear coefficient and concluded that the fundamental natural period can be successfully computed from 0.026 L; where L is the height of the building. This complies with a storey top drift angle of 1 / 200 for a base shear coefficient of 1 / (3 T). Therefore, the natural period T for multi-storey building is 0.026 L

But
$$T = \frac{2\pi}{\omega_{min}} = 0.026L$$

Therefore, according to Nakashima *et al.*, (1992) as reported by Dowling *et al.*, (1992);

$$\omega_{min} = \frac{2\pi}{T} = \frac{2\pi}{0.026L} = \frac{241.694}{L} \dots\dots\dots 18$$

Where, ω_{min} is the minimum natural frequency of the multi-storey building.

From equations 17 and 18, we have that

$$\frac{3EI_{on} \left(1 - \frac{4mgL^2}{\pi^2 EI_{on}} \right)}{mL^3} = \left(\frac{241.69}{L} \right)^2$$

and finally,

$$I_{on} = \frac{mL(19409.53 + 3.976L)}{E} \dots\dots\dots 19$$

Equation (19) is the modified generalised moment of inertia, corresponding to the odd modes of vibration of a multi-storey building under a steady state vibration.

m_i is the linear modal mass (LMM) which is given

$$m_i = \frac{ab\rho L}{3h_{sh}n_{sw}} \dots\dots\dots 20a$$

Multiplying equation (20a) by n_s (number of storeys), the total modal mass m (TMM) is given by

$$m = n_s m_i = \frac{n_s ab\rho L}{3h_{sh}n_{sw}} \dots\dots\dots 20b$$

where

n_{sw} = number of shear – walls along the investigated direction

$h_{sh} = L / n_s$ storey height of the shear – wall

a, b = dimensions of size of the building

ρ = density of the building

Substituting equation (20b) into equation (17), we have

$$\omega_{min} = \sqrt{\frac{3}{L^2} \left(1940953 + 3.975L - \frac{4gL}{\pi^2} \right)} \approx \frac{241.306}{L} \dots\dots\dots 21$$

This is the natural or angular frequency used by this study for the design of a multi-storey braced shear wall. The modified equations for the method of initial parameters are now as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} y(x) &= y_0 A_{k_{mx}} + \frac{\alpha_0}{k_m} B_{k_{mx}} + \frac{M_0 C_{k_{mx}}}{EI_{on}(k_m)^2} + \frac{Q_0 D_{k_{mx}}}{EI_{on}(k_m)^3} \\ \alpha(x) &= ky_0 D_{k_{mx}} + \alpha_0 B_{k_{mx}} + \frac{M_0 B_{k_{mx}}}{EI_{on}k_m} + \frac{Q_0 C_{k_{mx}}}{EI_{on}(k_m)^2} \dots\dots\dots 22a \\ M(x) &= EI_{on}(k_m)^2 y_0 C_{k_{mx}} + EI_{on}k_m \alpha_0 D_{k_{mx}} + M_0 A_{k_{mx}} + \frac{Q_0 B_{k_{mx}}}{k_m} \\ Q(x) &= EI_{on}(k_m)^3 y_0 B_{k_{mx}} + EI_{on}(k_m)^2 \alpha_0 C_{k_{mx}} + k_m M_0 D_{k_{mx}} + Q_0 A_{k_{mx}} \end{aligned}$$

The proposed modified influence functions for multi-storey building are given as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} A_{k_{mx}} &= 0.5 (\cosh k_{mx} + \cos k_{mx}) \\ B_{k_{mx}} &= 0.5 (\sinh k_{mx} + \sin k_{mx}) \\ C_{k_{mx}} &= 0.5 (\cosh k_{mx} - \cos k_{mx}) \\ \text{and } D_{k_{mx}} &= 0.5 (\sinh k_{mx} - \sin k_{mx}) \dots\dots\dots 22b \end{aligned}$$

Application of the Modified Method of Initial Parameters

- i. Determination of the Influence Functions for the Model

The influence functions are coefficients which depend on structural characteristics such as stiffness, mass and the overall length or height of the structural system been investigated. These parameters (influence functions) are also

critically influenced by the flexural rigidity of such systems. The corresponding influence functions derived for this work are:

$$\begin{aligned}
 A_{k_{mx}} &= 0.5 (\cosh k_{mx} + \cos k_{mx}) \\
 B_{k_{mx}} &= 0.5 (\sinh k_{mx} + \sin k_{mx}) \\
 C_{k_{mx}} &= 0.5 (\cosh k_{mx} - \cos k_{mx}) \\
 \text{and } D_{k_{mx}} &= 0.5 (\sinh k_{mx} - \sin k_{mx})
 \end{aligned}$$

From equation 7 and 22b, the results for the Kirlov's and modified influence functions are shown in Figures (2 and 3) respectively

Figure 2: Kirlov Influence Function

Figure 3: Proposed Influence Function

ii. Determination of the Fundamental Characteristic Mode of Vibration

When a structural system is disturbed by a time dependent load such as aerodynamic loadings from the original state of rest, the first elastic line it is forced to undergo is usually described as the Fundamental Characteristic Mode of

Vibration. This is very important for the design of tall structures because, the damping usually incorporated into the structural systems to absorb vibrations will usually not have significant influence on the first or characteristic mode of vibration.

Therefore, to determine this for this study, limiting values or boundary conditions such as $x = 0, y_0 = 0$, and $\alpha_0 = 0$ or $x = L, M_0 = 0$ and $y = L, Q_0 = 0$ were imposed on equation (22a) to give Table 1:

Table 1 -The complementary limiting equations (boundary conditions) for the initial parameters for the substitute cantilever (Darkov *et al.* 1979)

x	y(x)	$\alpha(x)$	M(x)	Q(x)
0	$\frac{M_0}{EI k^2} C_{kxm} + \frac{Q_0}{EI k^3} D_{kxm} = 0$	$\frac{M_0}{EI k^2} C_{kxm} + \frac{Q_0}{EI k^3} D_{kxm} = 0$	$M_0 A_{kxm} + \frac{Q_0}{k} C_{kxm} \neq 0$ 0	$k M_0 D_{kxm} + Q_0 A_{kxm} \neq 0$
L	$y_0 A_{kxm} + \frac{\alpha_0}{k} B_{kxm} \neq 0$	$k y_0 D_{kxm} + \alpha_0 B_{kxm} \neq 0$	$M_0 A_{kxm} + \frac{Q_0}{k} B_{kxm} = 0$	$k M_0 D_{kxm} + Q_0 A_{kxm} = 0$

The elastic line that describes the first or fundamental characteristic mode of vibration is obtained for the multi-storey building as:

$$y(x) = \frac{M_0 C_{kxm}}{EI_{on} k^2} + \frac{Q_0 D_{kxm}}{EI_{on} k^3} \tag{23a}$$

From equation (27a), M_0 and Q_0 can be determined by imposing the boundary or limiting conditions on Table 1. The values are given as

$$M_0 = \frac{EI_{on} y_0(L)}{C_{kxm} - \frac{A_{kxm} D_{kxm}}{B_{kxm}}} \tag{23b}$$

and $Q_0 = \frac{k A_{kxm} M_0}{B_{kxm}} \tag{23c}$

The logarithmic values of the results of the above analysis are shown in Figure 4

Using the values of the initial parameters obtained in Figure 4 the fundamental characteristic mode of vibration is determined as:

$$\eta_{ik} = \frac{\sum X_i(x) m_j}{\sum X_j^2(x) m_j} y(x) \quad \dots\dots\dots 24$$

(Malook *et al.*,1983 and Nakaskima 1992)

Where η_{jk} the coefficient of the normalised characteristic mode of vibration which is also equivalent to the amplitude A, of the first characteristic mode of vibration using the existing (Kirlov) and modified (proposed) methods of initial parameters. This was used to produce the histogram and logarithmic thresholds of vibration along the high rise building as shown in Figures (5 and 6) respectively.

Figure 5: Histogram of the Vibration Threshold along the Building Height

Figure 6; Logarithmic Curves of Vibration Thresholds along the Building

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The research results show that, it is possible to consider a high-rise building with rigid floors as a substitute cantilever flexural beam subjected to Euler critical load (Figure 1). As can be seen in Figures (2 and 3), when the method of initial parameter was super imposed with the influenced of Euler critical load, except A_{kx} and A_{kmx} that

remain almost asymptotic to unity; the remaining modified influence functions ($B_{k_{mx}}$, $C_{k_{mx}}$ and $D_{k_{mx}}$) generally became more sensitive along the model height. While the original Kirlov influence functions (B_{k_x} , C_{k_x} and D_{k_x}) became insensitive and converged with increase in model height and largely varies from 1.115 to 2.07 at the top of the model (Figure 2); the modified or proposed influence functions (Figure 3) remain very sensitive with increase in model height and varies between $2.85E-11$ to 1.0.

It is observed from Figure 2 that the bandwidth of the influence functions are wider at approximately 3.6 and converges as the height increases. At 72m height, their functions tend to meet. This behaviour is an indication of instability and may lead to concentration of stresses within the supporting structural members. This is therefore likely going to render these influence function unsuitable for use for the design of structures greater than 72m. Therefore, Kirlov's method is limited, uneconomical and unsafe for heights beyond 72m.

Figure 3 which is plot of the proposed method shows a marked improvement over the values obtained from Kirlov's method. The influence functions are sparsely distributed starting from the base of the model and remain highly sensitive with increase in height. The point of convergence which is 72m for Kirlov's method has been remarkably improved. This shows that a more stable and economical structure will be achieved using of this method of approach and can be applied for heights greater than 72m. The lesson to be learnt from this result is the fact that the Kirlov influence functions actually under valued the influence functions. This is largely due to the obvious fact that the total influence of the self weight (Euler Critical Load) has been neglected in the study. This actually means that the proposed method will sense and capable of evaluation infinitesimal or residual levels of vibrations that would have been ignored by the Kirlov model. This becomes very glaring from the values of $B_{k_{mx}}$, $C_{k_{mx}}$, and $D_{k_{mx}}$ respectively. Therefore, Figure 5 shows the histogram of vibration threshold along the building height. The result shows that the level of vibration increases with increase in building height but between 21.6 – 68.4 meters, the proposed method was able to sense smaller levels of vibration than Kirlov's solution.

Figure 4 shows the influence of the modified stiffness on the logarithmic characteristic values of the initial moment, and shear. It shows that, using the proposed method, the magnitude of the initial moment and shear are reduced by 14.67% and 37.98% respectively, and the stiffness improved very significantly over the values obtained by Kirlov.

Another implication or application of these results is that, even at this height of 72m, the influence of axial load has actually influenced the level of vibration of the entire structural system. It also proved as shown in Figures (5 and 6) that the histogram of vibration thresholds hitherto measured using the Kirlov influence functions may actually be identical but slightly affected using the proposed influence functions.

The proposed method in this paper considered the influence of Euler critical load very as necessary for the analysis of free vibrations of narrow rectangular buildings with shear-wall buildings. The formulae for the determination of the modified stiffness k , and moment of inertia I will be useful analytical tools for general structural dynamics and the assessment of the human comfort or perception rating of multi-storey buildings subjected to dynamic loadings. This is particularly a useful reference material for the students, researchers, experienced, inexperienced and practicing engineers for daily used for the design of tall structures (such as television or telecommunication masts and high – rise buildings) subjected to ponding or order forms of dynamic deflections or loadings including earthquakes.

CONCLUSION

- i. The study has developed a mathematical model that transformed the stiffness, k and moment of inertia, I values contained in the generalized governing equations for the method of initial parameters; from the one hitherto used for the design of beams on elastic foundation, to one suitable for the dynamic analysis of multi-storey building which is axially influenced by the Euler critical load.
- ii. The use of the Total Modal Mass (TMM) instead of the Linear Modal Mass (LMM) as used by Kirlov and many international codes of practice, has significantly improved the sensitivity of the influence functions by an average of about 99.987%.

- iii. The proposed method has influenced the assessment of the level of vibration thresholds of a multi-storey building when compared with the Kirlov's method which was originally used for dynamic analysis of beam on elastic foundation.
- iv. The structures with either the height greater than 50m, ratio (L / w) of height (L) and the least plan dimension (w) greater than 5 or minimum frequency less than unity; normally require that total dynamic analysis be carried out for such structures to avoid resonance. Therefore, since the use of Total Modal Mass (TMM) is capable of measuring the influence small changes (infinitesimal) in deflection or fundamental characteristic mode of vibration caused by the dynamic wind pulsation of the building. The implication of this is that, the infinitesimal or smaller influences of deformation or vibration will now be capable of being satisfactorily assessed by the proposed method. Therefore, it is advisable to use the formulae derived for the modified stiffness k_m , moment of inertia I_{on} and the Total Modal Mass (TMM) method instead of the Linear Modal Mass (LMM) method for such investigations.
- v. Regardless of all described above, a common trend between the Kirlov and the proposed influence functions is the fact that, apart from the values of A_{kx} and A_{kmx} that are almost asymptotic to unity (1.0), all other functions (i.e. B_{kx} , B_{kmx} , C_{kx} , C_{kmx} , D_{kx} and D_{kmx}) steadily increased with increase in height. This mean these values remain very sensitive with increase in height of the building. This trend has remarkably reflected the fact that angular frequency and consequently period is more critically influenced by the building or structure height. It is also to be observed that the overall height (L) will similarly influence the total modal mass of the structure. All these, therefore; agree with Nakashima et al (1992) that period T is approximately equal to 0.026 L.

RECOMMENDATIONS

On the basis of the findings during this research, the following recommendations were made to achieve a better structural analysis of multi-storey buildings or tall structures.

- i. The use of Total Modal Mass (TMM) instead of Linear Modal Mass (LMM) is hereby recommended; this will assist in achieving a better assessment of the true dynamic loading and consequently occupancy perception level or motion of the building when subjected to the dynamic wind pulsation.
- ii. This research has revealed that the stiffness and total modal mass (leading to the modified influence function) play useful role in the determination of angular frequency and consequently period of the model vibration.
- iii. The modified stiffness and moment of inertia will be useful tool for students, researchers, inexperienced and practicing engineers for daily used for the design of tall structures subjected to ponding or order forms of dynamic loadings.

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